

THE DRAPE FORMING OF A RUDDER TIP PREFORM

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the development of a drape forming method for a rudder tip preform. Shear characteristics of the glassfibre fabric were investigated using three different test methods, and a fabric lock angle was defined and measured. Simple fabric shear tests performed by hand were sufficient to define fabric shear limits for subsequent computer drape simulation trials.

Drape forming experiments and computer drape simulations showed good agreement overall. Drape simulation was found to be a very useful tool for designing preform manufacturing processes. In the drape forming of a rudder tip, it was demonstrated that a simple adjustment of the orientation of the forming tool was effective in distributing fabric shear more evenly over the part, eliminating wrinkling. Successful drape forming of $0/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies was achieved.

KEYWORDS: Drape simulation, fabric draping, fabric shear, intersection angle, preform.

INTRODUCTION

The CRC-ACS has made a number of advanced composite demonstrator components to showcase its preforming and liquid moulding technology. One of these components is a fibreglass/epoxy rudder tip, currently made by Aerospace Technologies of Australia from a fibreglass/epoxy prepreg, laid up by hand on a male mandrel, and cured in an autoclave. The CRC-ACS demonstrator component has been made by RTM; an important part of the success of this demonstrator component was the ability to drape the fibreglass fabric into the “deep draw” preform shape quickly and easily, without wrinkles or other defects. In particular the ability to shape the preform without the use of any ply drop-offs or internal splices was very desirable.

The paper first describes an investigation into the draping characteristics of the selected fibreglass fabrics. A very simple bench test was used, as well as mechanical tests on fabric samples. The second part of the paper discusses tests to determine how the fabric can be draped over the component mould shape. This section reports both experimental and computer simulation trials.

CURRENT PRODUCTION METHOD

The lay-up for the Rudder Tip fairing under investigation consists of eight plies of 302 gm/m², 8 harness satin, 1581-style prepreg and two plies of 107gm/m², 4 harness satin, 120-style glassfibre prepreg. The two 120-style prepreg plies are positioned on the part surfaces. This rudder tip part is 800 mm long, weighing 1300 gm and is currently laid up on a male mandrel. No orientation is specified for the prepreg lay-up. Debulking is required for after every two plies of prepreg. Considerable cutting and splicing is required to form the plies around the tight double curvature of the leading edge radius of the part, which makes the part expensive to produce. The very tacky nature of the prepreg used also causes problems in layup.

FABRIC SHEAR TESTS

Initial hand draping trials on the Rudder Tip mould showed that the double curvature of this part would test the limits of shear in the 1581 and 120 glass fabrics. To understand this aspect of draping, a very simple fabric shear limit test was performed. This involved laying the fabrics on a smooth flat surface and marking a 50mm square grid on the fabric along warp and weft directions. The fabric was then stretched by hand on the flat surface, until the fabric “locked”, with further stretching producing wrinkles and local lifting of the fabric off the surface. At this point load was removed and the “intersection angle”, α , between the grid in the warp and weft directions, was measured using a protractor. The shear deformation of the fabric, β , was then calculated from $\beta = 90^\circ - \alpha$. The intersection angle at which wrinkles appeared was defined in this study as the “fabric lock angle” α^* . The limit value of fabric shear, β^* , can be obtained from $\beta^* = 90^\circ - \alpha^*$. The simple method used here to measure the fabric shear limit produced results consistent with those of Skelton [1], who fully explains the mechanics of fabric shear.

Figure 1: A simple fabric shear limit test to measure lock angle, α^ .*

Figure 2: Shear limit test of 1581 fabric: α is 40° .

Figure 3: Wet 1581 fabric: α is 30° .

The test result for the 1581 style fabric is shown in Fig. 2. For 1581, an angle α of 40° was measured, while for the 120 fabric, an angle α of 30° was measured. A third test, with the 1581 cloth wetted by a low viscosity (room-temperature-curing) polyester resin, was also carried out. In this case, the fabric showed a significantly reduced α of 30° , as seen in Fig. 3. This improvement in fabric shear may be due to the lubrication effect of the resin, acting at tow crossovers, and also allowing easier reshaping of the tows for a tighter nesting of the fabric. The resin also provides tack, making the formation of wrinkles more difficult.

Two other sets of shear limit tests were carried out, with results made available for this study [2]. Simple bias extension tests were carried out on strips of fabric 120mm wide gripped in 80mm-wide jaws. A total fixed weight of 400gm on the lower jaw provided the only force. The fabric specimens were long enough to allow unrestrained deformation in the “gauge length”. Limit intersection angles were found to be 36° for the 1581 fabric and 35° for the 120 fabric. With fabrics wet with glycerine oil, the corresponding figures for α were 28° and 26° respectively.

Finally, dynamic testing using an Instron 1122A tensile test machine was carried out. The maximum capacity of the load cell used was 9.8N and the test speed used was 10mm/min. The test arrangement is shown in Fig. 4. In order to ensure correct installation of the specimen in the fixture, the fabric specimen with marked lines was mounted on the fixture on the bench, then the top half and bottom half of the fixture were rigidly connected using a connecting bar. The whole fixture was then installed in the jaws of the Instron machine and the connecting bar removed. The total length of the specimen was 320mm, with 220mm between two jaws (gross gauge length), 38mm clamped inside each jaw and 12mm projecting out from one side of each jaw. The width of the specimen was 100mm. Five specimens of each fabric were tested.

Figure 4: The clamping arrangement for the bias extension test.

Bias extension measurements in the gauge length were converted to intersection angles, and load was measured as force per unit width. The results are shown in Fig. 5. They indicate, as found previously, that 120-style fabric appears to drape more easily than 1581-style fabric, although this may be only because the 120 fabric is much lighter. The bias extension force for both fabrics increases substantially below $\alpha = 40^\circ$, but it is difficult from this test to define a precise lock angle α' .

Figure 5: Results of dynamic bias extension test.

HAND DRAPING TRIALS

Drape forming trials for the Rudder Tip were carried out on a forming mould which was a full-scale replica of the production male mandrel. The 1581 fabric was cut in $0/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ orientations, and a 50 mm square grid pattern was marked on the fabric to identify warp and weft directions. No drape trials were carried out on the 120 style fabric, as it was considered that this material was more easily formed than the 1581 fabric.

Figure 6: Mould drape angle, θ , achieved by angling either the fabric or the mould.

Initial drape trials using a 0/90° ply draped vertically, as in Fig. 6(a), showed a large amount of excess fabric at the front of the part, where the surface curves through an arc of 180°. It was found that this excess fabric could best be accommodated by sweeping the fabric on the side of the part rearward as shown in Fig. 6(b). In this way, the excess fabric at the front of the part was “shifted” to the rear of the part. The change in angle of the previously vertical fabric tows from the vertical is defined here as the mould drape angle, θ . (In this particular case only θ is also the shear angle of the fabric along the sides of the part).

In later trials, it was found that although the fabric could be swept back by hand to a measured angle θ , it was easier to raise the forming mould to the required angle θ , and allow the fabric to drape vertically, as shown in Fig. 6(c). The effect was identical. $\theta = 10^\circ$ was tried first. Bunching and wrinkling of fabric around the front of the part was greatly reduced, with most of the excess fabric moved along to the back of the part, past the trim line. However Fig. 8 shows that a few small wrinkles were present in the fabric around the front of the part, where intersection angles of 38° to 40° were measured, indicating that the fabric was at the limits of its ability to drape this shape.

Figure 7: 0/90 ply, $\theta = 0^\circ$: Excess fabric at the front of the part.

Figure 8: 0/90 ply, $\theta = 10^\circ$: Some minor wrinkles at the front of the part.

The mould drape angle was increased to $\theta = 20^\circ$, as shown in Fig. 9. This significantly reduced fabric shear at the front of the part, with more of the excess fabric being moved to the back of the part, past the trim line. The wrinkling problem was no longer evident and intersection angles measured were greater than 50° , even in the most highly stretched areas of the draped fabric.

Figure 9: 0/90 ply, $\theta = 20^\circ$: Successful draping, no wrinkles.

Similar trials were carried out, again using a single ply of 1581 fabric, with the ply orientation at $\pm 45^\circ$. Fig. 10 shows the symmetrical placement of the $\pm 45^\circ$ ply on the forming mould, which is horizontal (mould drape angle of 0°). A large excess of fabric was again found to accumulate around the front of the part. The amount of excess material in this case appeared to be greater than for the $0/90^\circ$ ply (see Fig. 7) at a 0° mould drape angle.

Again, an angling of the forming mould on which the $\pm 45^\circ$ ply was draped, resulted in a “redistribution” of the excess material around the front of the part, and the wrinkling problems were overcome. Figs. 11 & 12 show that with a drape angle of 10° , redistribution of the excess fabric occurred by a diagonal stretching of the fabric in three directions. Originating at the top of the leading edge (the point where the fabric first contacted the angled forming tool), lines of maximum stretch occurred along the centreline at the front, and symmetrically down the left and right sides of the forming tool. This redistribution of excess fabric occurred in a different manner to that observed with the $0/90^\circ$ plies, where the excess fabric was moved uniformly along the length of the part, past the rear trim line.

Figure 10: $\pm 45^\circ$ ply, $\theta = 0^\circ$; Excess fabric at the front of the part.

Figure 11: $\pm 45^\circ$ ply, $\theta = 10^\circ$; The excess fabric is redistributed.

Figure 12: $\pm 45^\circ$ ply, $\theta = 10^\circ$; another view.

Mould drape angles of 6.5° and 20° were also tried (see Table 1), with very similar results to those obtained using 10° . Maximum fabric shear results showed little variation (ie. $40-41^\circ$) for the range of tool angles trialed ($6.5-20^\circ$).

DRAPE SIMULATION

A computer drape simulation of the Rudder Tip shape was performed using the Patran 3 Laminate Modeller analysis package. This computer program fits a simulated fabric onto a finite element mesh of a part shape to produce a drape simulation. Laminate Modeller is based on the pin-joint net idealisation of a fabric which was first proposed by Mark and Taylor in 1956 [3]. This software model is based on the assumptions that: (i) tows are inextensible, and tow crossover points act as pin-joints with no relative slippage; and (ii) that tow segments are always straight between crossover points. Fabric shear is the only deformation mechanism allowed, and the fabric is fully in contact with the surface.

To simulate draping over a surface, it is necessary to show two intersecting lines on the part surface to simulate the tows in the fabric. This software package has some options for “globe draping” ie. draping on a highly curved surface. The option selected here was “geodesic,” which corrects for assumption (ii) by allowing curvature of the lines drawn from the starting point, (at the high point of the part) through the crossover points along geodesic paths on the surface. This method of draping control is most useful for an arbitrary three dimensional surface with double curvature.

The Patran3/Laminate Modeller simulations are shown below, in Figures 13 and 14. These simplified representations indicate warp and weft directions, from which can be found the intersection angles (α). Where shear in the fabric is predicted to be higher than the limit value (ie. areas where wrinkles may occur), the warp and weft lines are omitted for clarity. A limit value of shear deformation $\beta^* = 50^\circ$ was specified for this study, in line with the hand drape test results mentioned previously. The maximum predicted fabric shear, β_{max} , required to drape the Rudder Tip surface for the mould drape angles specified is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Predicted and measured maximum shear angles

Ply Orientation	Mould Drape Angle(θ)	Predicted β_{max}	Measured β_{max}
0/90°	0°	62.8°	>50°: Wrinkling
	10°	54.0°	52°: Small wrinkles
	20°	45.8°	40°
	26°	40.3°	No result
±45°	0°	70.0°	>50°: Wrinkling
	6.5°	42.9°	41°
	10°	46.0°	40°
	20°	45.5°	40°

Table 1 shows that the drape simulation predictions and the results of the hand draping experiments agree very well. For the 0/90° plies, the drape simulation predicted that β is well beyond the fabric shear limit β^* for the mould drape angle (θ) of 0°, and just beyond β^* for $\theta = 10^\circ$. This agrees well with the hand draping results, where draping was found to be impossible at $\theta = 0^\circ$, and marginal at $\theta = 10^\circ$, with only a few minor wrinkles.

For the ±45° plies, the simulation predicted that draping is not possible at $\theta = 0^\circ$; the hand draping experiments verified this, with a considerable excess of material at the front of the rudder tip at this angle. Draping was predicted to be possible, however, at $\theta = 6.5^\circ$, 10° and 20° ; hand draping confirmed this. Interestingly, draping was predicted to be slightly easier at 6.5° than 10° or 20° ; this could not be confirmed by the hand draping experiments.

Figure 13(a) & (b): 0/90° drape simulation.

Figure 14(a) & (b): ±45° drape simulation.

Comparison of Figures 10, 12 and 14 show that the general arrangement of the fabric is quite similar in simulation and experiment. In all cases the predicted β_{\max} was found to be from 2° to 6° higher than the measured β_{\max} in this shape. This may indicate that fabric shear is not the only mechanism operating, and that yarn slippage may also be occurring.

Significant differences can be noted in the way the 0/90° and ±45° plies drape around the rudder tip shape. Fig. 15 suggests the different deformation required. The 0/90° ply is stretched in the two “bias” directions at ±45° to the rudder tip leading edge, forming two highly-sheared fabric “ears”. Moderate shearing also occurs along the sides of the mould. The ±45° ply is stretched in three fabric bias directions at 0°, +90° and -90° to the mould leading edge, forming the ears mentioned above, but is not stretched appreciably along the sides or spine of the mould. The availability of three bias directions at the mould front for the ±45° ply gives it a wider arc of highly sheared fabric, apparently allowing it to fit the shape with a lower β_{\max} than the 0/90° ply. This improved ease of forming for the ±45° ply was evident in drape trials, where a small θ of 6.5° produced successful draping. For the 0/90° ply, it was necessary to increase mould drape angle to 20° to achieve successful draping.

Figure 15: Schematic of fabric shear for $0/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies.

CONCLUSIONS

Three types of test were used to establish the effective limit intersection angle for reinforcement fabrics. A very simple test performed by hand on a flat surface was the easiest of the three and was found to be sufficiently accurate for computer drape simulation trials.

It was demonstrated that the rudder tip geometry can be draped from one piece of fabric for both $0/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ ply orientations. The two fabric orientations differed in the characteristic way in which drape forming was achieved around the highly curved front of the rudder tip part. The methods developed using single fabric plies, are expected to facilitate the production of a multi-ply rudder tip preform.

Comparison of drape simulation predictions and hand draping experiments indicated good agreement overall. Drape simulation is therefore a useful tool, particularly when the mould/tool is not available for draping experiments.

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